

How to arm a castle: the 1346 ordonnance of Bioule

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Abstract

The study presents the first full English translation of the 1346 ordonnance describing the defenses of the Bioule castle (Tarn-et-Garonne, France). This is one of the most specific documents on the organization of medieval castle defense to have survived to this day, presenting a nearly exhaustive picture of the exact locations of various pieces of artillery with accessories and ammunition, their crews and other soldiers of the garrison. The various aspects of Bioule castle defenses are discussed and visualized on the castle plan.

Introduction

The ordonnance of Bioule is a unique document warranting a deeper examination of it. These very precise regulations were issued for the garrison of the Bioule castle located on the bank of Aveyron river in Tarn-et-Garonne, France. Thanks to the very early mention of 22 canons (the actual count seems to be 25), this ordinance has received a lot of exposure in research addressing the development of firearms. However, it is also exemplary in its providing extensive information on several other aspects of castle defense: crossbows of various types, men performing a range of functions on the fortifications; reference to the specific towers, and several additional orders regarding the organization of defense.

Bioule castle in its 1346 was largely a mixture of a 13th century structure with modifications made in 1329 and consequent years. It is built largely of brick, with a quantity of stone used in the foundations and first floors of some structures and has a rectangular plan ca. 100 x 50 m in size. It sits on the bank of the river Aveyron, just next to an elongated island; the builders took advantage of this position and placed a water mill on the narrow channel separating the castle and the island. See Figures 2-5 for various modern views of the castle. The castle is divided into two courtyards, with the western half consisting of the residential buildings, the donjon (ruined) and chapel, while the eastern half largely does not survive to this day but presumably contained the well (extant), smithy, stables and other service buildings.

It would be most useful to subject the text of this ordonnance to a meticulous inquiry. While other comparable 14th century documents do exist (e.g. Lille, Agen, Tournay), none provide quite as much detail. I therefore include a full English translation, omitting the original Occitan text which can be found in [1].

Translation of the original text of the ordonnance

This is the ordinance made regarding the way people will be distributed around the defenses, at the castle of Bioule; which was made by Monseigneur Hugues de Cardailhac, lord of Bioule, on the Sunday before Palm Sunday, the year 1346.

1. First, in front of the exterior gate, on the watchtower,

1.1 Two men to shoot the springald.

1.2 More, another two in this same place, to fire the guns. And in case (the enemy) would have advanced to the wall, let those of the springalds throw large stones: and these will be on the first floor.

1.3 Also, on the upper floor, two crossbowmen to fire one-foot crossbows.

1.4 Also, another two in this same place, to throw stones and shoot the slings.

1.5 Plus, in the same place, one or two men-at-arms to support them.

1.6 Plus, there is a springald.

1.7 Plus, two crossbows and two loading hooks.

1.8 Plus, a two-foot crossbow and a loading lever.

1.9 Plus, four cannons and two *desarras*.

1.10 Plus, ten buckets full of quarrels, and large and small stones.

1.11 Plus, four slings.

2. The second defense.

2.1 Plus, **on the new tower facing the house of S. Beche**, there are two crossbowmen.

2.2 Plus, two men to fire the cannons.

2.3 Plus, two men to throw the stones and shoot the slings.

2.4 Plus, two men-at-arms.

2.5 Plus, two one-foot crossbows and two loading hooks, and four cannons and two *desarras*.

2.6 Plus, buckets full of quarrels to shoot at the enemies, if they come, and plenty large and small stones.

2.7 Also, four slings.

2.8 Plus, between this tower and the Crowned tower, there are two crossbowmen to shoot stones with crossbows. [This item confusing. The original text reads “Item, d’aquela tor entro la tor coronada y aia dos balesties per trayre peyra am las balestas”. In principle, crossbows designed to shoot small round stones or bullets are known from other 14th-15th century sources. Or perhaps this should be understood as “two crossbowmen who throw stones and have crossbows?”]

3. The third defense on the Crowned tower.

3.1 There shall be two men to shoot with the winch-loaded crossbow.

3.2 Plus, two men to fire the cannons.

3.3 Also, another two men to throw stones.

3.4 Plus, one man on this tower, one winch-loaded crossbow and one winch. [the “man” is probably meant as “man-at-arms”]

3.5 Plus, two one-foot crossbows, and two loading hooks, three guns and two *desarras*.

3.6 Also, clay buckets full of quarrels, and large and small stones, and two slings.

4. The fourth defense is on the watchtower which is on the New tower, next to the well.

4.1 Two men to fire the winch-loaded crossbow.

4.2 Plus, a crossbowman to shoot a one-foot crossbow.

4.3 Plus, a man to fire the cannons. And we place on the said watchtower a crossbow and a winch.

4.4 Plus, two one-foot crossbows and two hooks.

4.5 Plus, two cannons and two *desarras*.

4.6 Plus, ten buckets full of bolts, enough large and small stones and four slings.

5. The fifth defense is at the gate which is in front of the square.

5.1 On the first floor, two men to fire the cannons and to throw large stones.

5.2 And on the second floor, two men to shoot the two-foot crossbow.

5.3 Plus, on the wall, two crossbowmen.

5.4 Plus, two more men to throw fist-sized rocks and a man-at-arms. And we shall put on this defense a two-foot crossbow and a loading lever.

5.5 Plus, three one-foot crossbows, and three loading hooks, and three cannons, and two *desarras*.

5.6 And ten buckets full of bolts, and plenty large and small stones, and four slings.

5.7 Plus, **between this watchtower and the tower of the oven**, two men to throw stones in the covered gallery.

6. The sixth defense is on the tower facing the oven.

6.1 On the said tower, two men to fire the springald which is there.

6.2 Plus, a crossbowman and another man throwing stones. And let them put in the tower a springald, and two one-foot crossbows, and two loading hooks, and two guns, and two *desarras*, and four slings, and enough large and small stones.

6.3 Plus, **in the watchtower above the belfry**, two crossbowmen. And let there be two one-foot crossbows, and two hooks, and ten clay buckets full of bolts, and four slings, and many large and small stones.

6.4 Plus, **between this tower and the tower which is on the pantry, in the covered gallery**, three men throwing stones.

7. The seventh defense is on the watchtower of the tower, which stands above the mill.

7.1 Two men to fire a winch-loaded crossbow.

7.2 Plus, two men to fire the cannons.

7.3 Plus, a crossbowman. And let them put there a winch-loaded crossbow, and a winch, and a two-foot crossbow and a loading lever.

7.4 Plus, two one-foot crossbows and two loading hooks.

7.5 Plus, four slings, and enough large and small stones.

7.6 Plus, clay buckets full of quarrels.

8. The eighth defense is on the big tower (or donjon).

8.1 There shall be two men at the winch-loaded crossbow.

8.2 Plus, another two [men] for another winch-loaded crossbow.

8.3 Plus, four one-foot crossbows.

8.4 Plus, two men to fire the two-foot crossbow.

8.5 Plus, two men to fire the cannons. And we put in the said tower two winch-loaded crossbows and two winches.

8.6 Plus, two two-foot crossbows.

8.7 Plus, a loading lever.

8.8 Plus, six one-foot crossbows.

8.9 Plus, four belt hooks.

8.10 Plus, four guns and two *desarras*.

8.11 Plus, clay buckets full of bolts to shoot at enemies.

8.12 Plus, eight slings.

8.13 More, enough fist-sized and large stones.

[The following contains some general remarks on how the castle defenses are organized]

8.14 More, let none of these get in the way of each other, and let them shoot first, if the enemies come, the winch-loaded crossbows which reach farther, and then afterwards with two-foot crossbows and [then] with stones and cannons in such manner as they see fit for defense.

8.15 Next, in each of these aforesaid defenses there shall be an officer whom all the others shall obey.

8.16 Moreover, in case alarm will be raised, no man must be frightened, and let everyone go to their posts. And we shall provide to each of the officers their men in their harness. And whoever is not there will be severely punished.

8.17 Plus, let the captain of each guard be given the artillery he will need. And he must see to it that the artillery does not go to perdition. And this one has to take care that he has good artillery and all [other] that he needs.

8.18 More, let there be plenty of dead sulfur, and plenty of live sulfur, and saltpeter, and camphor, and ice (?), and all that is needed to make gunpowder, or to set fires on the castles or cats [war machines] of those outside [i.e. the enemies].

8.19 Moreover, in addition to the above, on the donjon there are always two sentries who take guard if they see companions. [They probably greeted the incoming friendly contingents with banners and/or trumpets, as per military tradition]

8.20 And do not light a fire on the watchtowers, but in the braziers, because it is dangerous.

In total, 17 crossbowmen are needed for the defenses and 10 men-at-arms.

The total of men at the defenses of the entire castle, including the men-at-arms, crossbowmen and other combatants, 70 men.

In total, required for all the defenses are 5 winch-loaded crossbows and winches; 5 two-foot crossbows and 5 loading levers; 24 one-foot crossbows and 24 hooks; 2 stirrup crossbows [?]; 38 slings; 2 springalds; 14 *desarras*, and 22 cannons.

[The separate entries for 24 one-foot crossbows and 2 stirrup crossbows are confusing. The two terms seem to be identical and refer to the same kind of small crossbow with a stirrup that could be spanned with a belt hook. However, the stirrup crossbows could also be of the larger type that required a lever to be spanned, making them equivalent to two-foot crossbows.]

Discussion

1) The ordonnance is very specific and refers to each tower of the castle, except for the Tower of the Pantry (the middle of the southern wall) and two watchtowers on the south-eastern corner. The post of each man was clearly defined; in the case of attack, they didn't rush to the walls in a pall-mall fashion but rather took their posts and performed the specific functions they were trained for. Each tower had its own captain who oversaw all aspects of local defense, including ammunition supply, condition of the armaments and performance of men. It is also remarkable that the tower names are still known and can be identified with the standing and demolished parts of the castle. Taking advantage of this specificity, I present a visualization of all armaments mentioned in the text in Figure 1. This plan was developed using the sketch in [2].

2) The castle of Bioule is quite compact (100 x 50 m), and its towers are relatively small. Therefore, the distribution of men, crossbows, guns and ammunition became a task requiring exhaustive knowledge of the spaces available, and the chance of attack from different directions. The lord of Cardailhac might have made the assessment by himself, or, which I find more likely, worked from his advisors' opinions.

3) The larger crossbows seem to have been installed in covered spaces of the tower floors, which was perhaps motivated by the need to protect the hardware from the weather and protect it from enemy fire. The size of the rooms, which was relatively small as noted above, must have presented significant limitations to what weapons could be deployed. The loading tools of the crossbows, the lever (*aussa-premp*) and winch (*torn*) took up a lot of space by themselves. The winch-loaded crossbow was about 1.5-2 m in size and maybe 12-25 kg in weight and had to be carried to the bench with the winch and then back to the shooting position. The springald was an even bulkier contraption at least 2x3 m in size, that also required free space on all sides to be aimed, reloaded and shot.

4) The planners of defense also gave a lot of thought on how to optimize artillery fire taking into account the effective distance of each of the weapon types. Here, one finds uniquely specific

information on weapon distance rating: springald – two-foot crossbow – cannons & stones (maybe meaning the slings). The winch-loaded crossbow and small stirrup crossbows are not mentioned, but represent the two further firing distances, bringing the total of the distance classes to five. The ordonnance keeps this point schematic, one stating the main principle of distance optimization, but leaving detailed planning to others (probably the captains of each tower).

5) Relatively few posts were ascribed to the sections of the walls between the towers. Only seven men, or about 10% of the garrison, were positioned on the walls, most or all of them inside covered galleries. The rest took posts inside or on the towers.

6) The points about the preparation of gunpowder, sentries who give signals from the donjon, the lighting of fire are other unique insights into the life of a castle.

7) The cannons of this early period have been discussed at length in other studies, and it seems to be uncertain whether they were of the most primitive type shooting arrows and mounted on table-like footings, or already represented primitive hand cannons seen in later 14th – 15th century art. I am inclined to think that they were small hand-held cannons, as the castle simply doesn't have enough rooms to accommodate guns of larger size, as they were all occupied by crossbows and springalds.

8) The weapons are accompanied by their specific loading devices, which were of course a prerequisite of their operation – the winch, the lever, the belt hooks. The unclear term *desarras* that accompanies the cannons is, therefore, likely to mean ramrod or some other cannon accessory.

9) No detailed planning was made for the types of crossbow and cannon ammunition stocks. The text repeatedly mentions *pechies* full of bolts. The four crossbow classes all used bolts of substantially different sizes, which in practice had to be kept separately. The cannon ammunition is not mentioned at all. The *pechies* were probably large buckets or baskets that could hold about 30 kg (60 pounds) of grain, and are specifically said to have had an earthenware shell – to prevent moisture damage to the ammunition. Most towers contained 10 buckets of bolts, sometimes less; based on many other sources, we can expect each weapon to have had from 50-100 (springalds) to 100-300 (winch crossbow and two-foot crossbow) to several hundred bolts (one-foot crossbow).

10) Many men had the specific function of stone throwers. One should not underestimate the power of this prehistoric weapon!

11) There is a considerable mismatch between the numbers of men given in the end of the original text and the figures obtained by summation of the entries in the detailed description. Regarding the count of men, the three uncertainties are related to the sentries and captains: if they should be added to the staff mentioned in the points 1.1-8.15, it makes the total count equal to 81. This is 11 more than the figure of 70 given in the original text after 8.20. However, if the captains and sentries were selected from among the rest of the garrison, this reduces the total to 71. I count 8 captains but the total could well be 9 – therefore producing the total of 70. Nevertheless, there is another mismatch in the number of men-at-arms: in 1.1-8.15, we find a total of 6 soldiers, while in the end of the document 10 are stated. The number of cannons is 22

in the sum original text, while the sum of the cannons in 1.1-8.15 is actually 25. The respective counts for one-foot crossbows are 24 and 25.

Glossary of the weapons mentioned

Balesta d'estrop – crossbow with a stirrup (size class 1)

Balesta de I pe – one-foot crossbow (size class 1)

Balesta de dos pes – two-foot crossbow (size class 2)

Balesta de torn – “winch crossbow”, i.e. a large crossbow that is loaded with a table-mounted winch (size class 3)

Espingala – springald, a large crossbow with an integral winch or screw-driven loading device, mounted on a static footing (size class 4)

croc – belt hook used to draw the string of one-foot crossbows

Ausa-premp (Occ.) = *haussepren* (Fr.) – loading lever used to draw the string of mid-range crossbows, literally “tall leg”, a lever on a wheeled or static platform used to draw the string of mid-sized crossbows. In this text, *haussepieds* are used to load two-foot crossbows.

Torn – crossbow-loading winch

flagelada – staff sling

canon – cannon

cairel – quarrel/bolt, crossbow and springald projectile

pechie (Occ.) = *bichete* (Fr.) – a bucket; a measure of grain equal to 60 pounds (see DuCange-bichetus), a large bucket or a small barrel

desarra – a word of unknown origin, a previous French edition of this ordonnance proposes the meaning of “wedge” or “loosener”, in the sense of a tool used to mount or dismount the cannon barrel from its wooden tiller. I think it could have been the ramrod.

**Bioule castle defenses:
the ordonnance of 1346**

Pavel Alekseychik / Medieval Advisor 2023

Figure 1. Visualization of weapons and garrison mentioned in the Bioule ordonnance of 1346.

*the mismatch in the number of men-at-arms, see point 11 of Discussion for details.

Figure 2. The modern aerial view of the castle of Bioule (© Google Earth).

Figure 3. The view of the castle from the west, showing the western gate, the

Figure 4. The remaining western half of the southern side of the castle which contained the residential areas; the tower of the oven (center) and the Pantry tower (right) are seen.

Figure 5. Aerial view of the castle and town of Bioule.

References

[1] The original Occitan text of the Bioule ordonnance (p. 490):

<https://books.google.fi/books?id=G8h3RhkWb8YC&pg=PA496&lpg=PA496&dq=%22Bioule%22+%22la+tour+couronnee%22&source=bl&ots=PX9W-2WpFY&sig=ACfU3U2KYeWn9rLv5X5NGwDrMyLGqCw0Vg&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwieov3-vaSAAxVsFBAIHfa9BTQQ6AF6BAgMEAM#v=onepage&q=%22la%20tour%20couronnee%22&f=false>

[2] Bioule castle plan:

<https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6532228m/f35.item.r=bioule.zoom>